

Prevalence of Congenital Abnormalities on Routine Ultrasound Scan of Second Third Trimester Pregnancy in Guru Govind Singh Sadar Hospital, Patna City, Patna, Bihar, India.

Shikha Rani¹, Rajiv Kumar²

¹MBBS, MD (Radiodiagnosis), Senior Medical Officer (SMO), Guru Govind Singh Hospital, Patna City, Patna, Bihar, India.

²Professor & Head, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Netaji Subhas Medical College & Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India.

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Shikha Rani

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Objectives: The present study was to evaluate the sociodemographic profile of anomaly positive women, prevalence, and type of congenital abnormalities in second and third trimester on ultrasonography scanning.

Methods: The Radiologist performed all the transabdominal ultrasonography on a 'Z6- Mindray color Doppler ultrasound system' after taking verbal consent from the patient. A questionnaire was used containing the following information e.g. women's age, parity, gravidity, date of last menstrual period. The questionnaire form also included about the result of transabdominal USG examination which included the following: singleton or multiple, dead, or alive foetus, gestational age, and presence or absence of congenital anomalies.

Results: A total 954 women of 2nd and 3rd trimester pregnancy were enrolled. Rate of prevalence of congenital abnormalities was 1.57%. Majorities of fetus anomaly positive women 10(66.67%) were in age group of 20-35 years. Most of the women had primary school level of education. Most of the women were nulliparous 7(46.67%) and primiparous 5(33.33%). Most of the women 9(60%) were in 2nd trimester of pregnancy. Live foetus at time of scanning were seen in 13(86.67%) women. Intra uterine death foetus at time of scanning was seen in 2(13.33%) women. Multiple pregnancy was seen in 2(13.33%) women. central nervous system anomalies 10(66.67%), gastro-intestinal anomalies 5(33.33%) and others anomalies 5(33.33%) were the most common. Anencephaly 4(26.67%) and hydrocephalus 2(13.33%) were the common CNS anomalies. Duodenal atresia 2(13.33%) was the common gastro-intestinal anomaly.

Conclusions: Rate prevalence of congenital abnormalities was 1.57%. Central nervous system anomaly was the most common followed by gastro-intestinal anomalies. Anencephaly and hydrocephalous were the most common central nervous system anomalies. Duodenal atresia was the common gastro-intestinal anomalies. Hence, the routine ultrasonography scanning is one of the best choices of diagnostic tool during the 2nd and 3rd trimester of pregnancy to detect foetal abnormalities.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Birth defects are a major contributor to perinatal and infant mortality, morbidity, and lifelong disability worldwide. Birth defects affect at least 3% of babies in most populations [1,2]. The anomalies are the leading cause of neonatal morbidity & mortality. Defective embryogenesis or intrinsic abnormalities in the process of development result congenital anomalies. About 3,03,000 newborns die within 4 weeks of birth every year worldwide due to congenital anomalies [3].

All pregnancies are at a risk of producing congenital malformations, though only some of them are at a greater risk. There is a need for routine and thorough screening for foetal congenital anomalies. The priority goal in

screening is the early detection of major foetal anomalies [4, 5]. The National Health Service (NHS) Foetal Anomaly Screening Program guidance recommends screening for conditions with detection rates above 50% at this scan, including anencephaly, open spina bifida and gastroschisis. 'Defined ultrasound findings of uncertain significance' or 'normal variants' (referred to as 'markers') are also identified at this scan. These include echogenic bowel (EB), renal pelvicalyceal dilatation (PCD) and cardiac echogenic foci (CEF). Associations between markers and adverse pregnancy outcomes including intrauterine fetal death, chromosomal abnormalities and cystic fibrosis have been reported [6].

Congenital anomalies may present as isolated abnormalities or part of a syndrome. The most common, severe anomalies include congenital heart defects, cleft lip with or without cleft palate, Down syndrome & neural tube defects [7,8]. Laboratory test and imaging studies are available for detection of these anomalies. Ultrasound examination is one of the most important diagnostic tools which give a great amount of information about the anatomical structure as well as some physiological aspect of the status of the foetus. The current ACR (American College of Radiology)/ AIUM (American Institute of Ultrasound in Medicine) guidelines for the performance of the second & third trimester obstetrics examination describe the standard sonographic examination [9].

The guidelines help to maximize detection of many foetal abnormalities. The level-I (Standard or routine) ultrasound scan is performed routinely on pregnant woman. This examination scans maternal uterus, ovaries, cervix, and placenta, as well as a systematic review of foetal anatomy. In high-risk cases, targeted or level-II scan is indicated for a detailed foetal sonogram. The level-II scan is specifically indicated when an anomaly is suspected because of maternal medical or family history, or any abnormality of the foetus is suspected on a routine scan. In general, the standard foetal anatomic survey refers to the second trimester scan performed between 16 and 22 weeks of gestation. When anatomic surveys are performed at 20 & 22 weeks gestational age, there is less need for repeat scan [10]. If a major structural defect is identified, termination of pregnancy is offered, as morbidity and mortality of this procedure increases with advancing gestation [11]. Diagnostic ultrasound examination may be employed in a variety of specific circumstances during pregnancy, such as after the occurrence of clinical complications or when concerns about foetal growth exist. Because adverse outcomes may

also occur in pregnant women without clear risk factors, assumptions have been made that routine ultrasound in all pregnancies will prove to be beneficial by enabling earlier detection and improved management of pregnancy complications [12]. Objective of our study was to evaluate the sociodemographic profile of anomaly positive women, prevalence, and type of congenital abnormalities in second and third trimester on ultrasonography scanning.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted in the Guru Govind Singh Sadar hospital, Patna city, Patna, Bihar during a period from February 2023 to March 2024.

A total of 954 second and third trimester pregnant women were enrolled in the present study. Data was collected by using systematic sampling methods.

Procedure: The Radiologist performed all the transabdominal ultrasonography on a 'Z6- Mindray color Doppler ultrasound system' after taking verbal consent from the patient. A questionnaire was used containing the following information e.g. women's age, parity, gravidity, date of last menstrual period. The questionnaire form also included about the result of transabdominal USG examination which included the following: singleton or multiple, dead or alive foetus, gestational age, and presence or absence of congenital anomalies. All the sociodemographic profile including gestational age were recorded.

Results

A total 954 women of 2nd and 3rd trimester pregnancy were enrolled in the present study. Among them, anomaly positive women were 15(1.57%). Rate of prevalence was 1.57%. Majorities of fetus anomaly positive women 10(66.67%) were in age group of 20-35 years.

Figure 1: Age group of anomaly positive group of women (N=15).

Among the anomaly positive women, most had primary school level of education. Most of the women were nulliparous 7(46.67%) and primiparous 5(33.33%). Most of the women 9(60%) were in 2nd trimester of pregnancy.

Table 1: Showing the literacy of anomalies positive women (N=15).

Literacy	No. of women	Percentage
Illiterate	4	26.67%
Primary schooling	7	46.66%
>Primary schooling	4	26.67%
Total	15	100%

Table 2: Showing the parity of anomalies positive women (N=15).

Parity	No. of women	Percentage
0	7	46.67%
1	5	33.33%
2	2	13.33%
3	1	6.66%
Total	15	100%

Figure 2: Showing the gestational age (N=15).

In the present study, Live foetus at time of scanning were seen in 13(86.67%) women. Intra uterine death foetus at time of scanning was seen in 2(13.33%) women. Multiple pregnancy was seen in 2(13.33%) women.

Table 3: Showing the results of USG of anomaly positive group of women (N=15).

Variables	No. of women(N=15)	Percentage
Live foetus at time of scanning	13	86.67%
Intra uterine death foetus at time of scanning	2	13.33%
Multiple pregnancy	2	13.33%
Multiple anomaly of foetus	1	6.66%

Ultrasonographic findings shown that the central nervous system anomalies 10(66.67%), gastro-intestinal anomalies 5(33.33%) and others anomalies 5(33.33%) were the most common anomalies. Among the CNS anomalies, anencephaly 4(26.67%) and hydrocephalus 2(13.33%) were the common anomalies. Duodenal atresia 2(13.33%) was the common gastro-intestinal anomaly.

Table 4: Showing anomalies involving different system (N=15).

Category	Pattern of anomaly	No. of women (N=15)	Percentage
Central nervous system (N=10)	Hydrocephalus	2	13.33%
	Anencephaly	4	26.66%
	Microcephaly	1	6.66%
	Meningomyoceles	3	20%
Musculo skeletal (N=1)	Skeletal dysplasia	1	6.66%
Gastro intestinal (N= 5)	Duodenal atresia	2	13.33%
	Diaphragmatic hernia	1	6.66%
	Omphelocele	1	6.66%
	Gastro schiasis	1	6.66%
Genito urinary (N=2)	Pelvi – ureteric junction obstruction	1	6.66%
	Polycystic kidney	1	6.66%
Others (N=5)	Hydrops foetalis	2	13.33%
	Conjoined twin	1	6.66%
	Cystic hygroma	1	6.66%
	Down syndrome	1	6.66%

Discussions

Congenital foetal anomalies have been the concern of obstetricians and society for many centuries. A congenital foetal abnormality often results in spontaneous abortion or perinatal death, commonly associated with prematurity or major handicap including mental retardation (13).

Three ultrasound screening examinations during pregnancy are recommended in Latvia. The 1st US screening is performed at the 11th to 13th week of pregnancy, the 2nd is performed at the 20th to 21st week, and the 3rd is performed at 34–36 weeks for at-risk pregnant women [12]. Prenatal ultrasound (US) screening can help to monitor normal foetal development and screen for any potential problems. Patients undergoing prenatal ultrasound should be made aware of the limitations of this tool in detecting anomalies. Prenatal detection has several practical benefits, including parental preparation, delivery planning, and the provision of optimal paediatric care [12, 14]. Prenatal screening for the detection of foetal anomalies is organized by laws and guidelines [15]. Oakley et al. [16] reported that the prevalence of foetal anomalies at birth ranged from 2% to 5% in general populations. In the United States and Europe, the rates of foetal anomalies at birth have been reported to be 3.0% and 2.4%, respectively [17,2]. In Saudi Arabia, the prevalence of foetal anomalies at birth was reported to be 4.6% [18]. The primary factors that affect the prevalence of foetal anomalies in different populations are consanguinity, use of assisted reproduction techniques, tobacco exposure, air pollution, water contamination and pesticide and agrochemical exposure [19, 20].

In the present study, a total 954 women with second and third trimester of pregnancy were participated and undergone for ultrasonography scanning examination. Among them, 15 women had positive

foetus anomalies. Rate of prevalence was 1.57%. Which is comparable with the observations of Nakling et al [21] 1.47%, and Souka et al [22] 1.21%. Higher prevalence was observed some other studies like Sallout et al [23] 2.96%, Alia et al [24] 2.97%, Dolk et al [2] 2.39% and Yanuarman et al [25] 4.1% in Hasan Sadikin General Hospital in Bandung.

Naseha and Iqbal [26] reported that family history of congenital anomaly was seen in 7.2%, which is less than the incidence reported by Christianson et al. [27]. Due to early detection of most lethal anomaly, termination was done in 35% and IUFD occurred in 2.2%. In non-lethal anomaly and a few lethal anomalies diagnosed, late early neonatal death occurred in 4.4% and late neonatal death in 0.6%.

In the present study, majorities of fetus anomaly positive women 10(66.67%) were in age group of 20-35 years. Most of the women were nulliparous and primary parous.

This variation may be due to different geographical area, social factor, racial difference, observer variation and equipment quality [28, 29]. As true prevalence of congenital anomalies depends upon several factors and therefore two studies are never strictly comparable. Though elderly age group and higher parity are considered as risk factors for congenital anomaly. In our study the incidence was observed higher in nulligravida and primigravida and younger age group. This may be due to earlier age of marriage in our scanning population.

Yanuarman et al. [25] stated that most of the women having congenital anomalies in the foetus were primigravida and aged between 20-35 years old. Our study suggested age of 20-35 years old as the risk factor of congenital anomalies.

In the present study, among congenital anomaly, central nervous system anomaly had the highest 10(66.67%) followed by 5(33.33%) gastrointestinal system anomaly and others anomaly. Anencephaly (26.66), hydrocephalus 2(13.33%) and meningomyoceles 3(20%) were the common central nervous system anomaly. This finding is similar to Yanuarman et al. [25], Agarwal et al.,[30] and Parveen et al. [31]. There was no congenital heart anomaly found in the present study.

A previous study in a general population reported a first-trimester detection rate of 90% for complex congenital heart disease (either alone or in association with extracardiac abnormalities) and 69.5% for complex central nervous system anomalies [32]. Detection of foetal anomalies in the third trimester is technically more challenging due to foetal growth, poor imaging with static ultrasound and decreased quantities of amniotic fluid [33]. Other studies have evaluated the sensitivity of ultrasound for diagnosing foetal anomalies in the third trimester [33, 34].

Antenatal care is an important predictor of favourable childbirth outcomes. The increasing tendency of US screening during pregnancy is reflected in routine statistical data in Latvia among births in the last decade—an increase in US screening from 60% to 90% in the 1st trimester—as well as the same tendency in the 2nd and 3rd trimesters of pregnancy [35]. The same tendency was found in France, where the number of US examinations per pregnancy increased over time, and the prenatal detection rate of foetal anomalies has not increased in recent years. These data suggest that there is a need to implement policies to improve the efficacy of US examinations for the prenatal diagnosis of congenital anomalies, including the provision of more high-quality training programmes [36]. Another study also mentioned that the training levels of ultrasound providers may affect detection rates [37].

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the rate prevalence of congenital abnormalities was 1.57%. Central nervous system anomaly was the most common followed by gastro-intestinal anomalies. Anencephaly and hydrocephalous were the most common central nervous system anomalies. Duodenal atresia was the common gastro-intestinal anomalies. Hence, the routine ultrasonography scanning is one of the best choices of diagnostic tool during the 2nd and 3rd trimester of pregnancy to detect foetal abnormalities.

References

1. The Global Health Network. Global Birth Defects. <https://globalbirthdefects.tghn.org/about-us/>
2. Dolk H, Loane M, Garne E. The prevalence of congenital anomalies in Europe. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 2010; 686:349–64.
3. References: 1. Congenital anomalies. World Health Organization (WHO) Fact sheet. Updated September 2016. Available at: <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs370/en/> [Accessed on January 12, 2017].
4. Sepulveda W, Cafici D, Bartholomew J et al. First-trimester assessment of the fetal palate: a novel application of the Volume NT algorithm. *J Ultrasound Med* 2012; 31: 1443–1448.
5. Swetha B, Ravi G, Bharathi M et al. Evaluation of the Incidence of Congenital Fetal Malformations by Sonography in the Second Trimester. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research* 2016; 2(9): 2454-1362.
6. Kirwan D. 18 + 0 to 20 + 6 weeks fetal anomaly scan. In *National Standards and Guidance for England. NHS Fetal Anomaly Screening 2010: 1-79*. https://cerpo.cl/_items/File_002_00420_0_030.pdf.
7. Lin AE, Herring AH, Amstutz KS, Westgate MN, Lacro RV, Al-Jufan M, et al. Cardiovascular Malformations: changes in prevalence and birth status, 1972-1990. *Am J Med Genet*. 1999; 84 (2): 102-10.
8. Wen SW, Liu S, Joseph KS, Rouleau J, Allen A. Patterns of infant mortality caused by major congenital anomalies. *Teratology*. 2000; 61 (5) :342-6.
9. Begum SA, Nishat L, Mannan A, Rahman T, Rahman Y. Prevalence of Congenital Anomalies Detected by the Second Trimester Ultrasound Scan in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Bangladesh. *Eastern Med Coll J*. 2017; 2 (2): 5-9.
10. Rumack CM, Ed. *Diagnostic ultrasound*, 4th ed. USA: Mosby; 2011: 1041-1058.
11. Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists. *Termination of Pregnancy for Fetal Abnormality in England, Scotland and Wales. Report of A Working Party, May 2010*. Available at: <https://www.rcog.org.uk/global-assets/documents/guidelines/terminationpregnancyreport18may2010.pdf> [Accessed on January 10, 2017]
12. Regulations of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 611. Procedures for providing childbirth assistance (in Latvian) <https://likumi.lv/ta/id/140695-dzemdibu-palidzibas-nodrosinasanas-kartiba>.
13. Jørgensen D, Vejlsttrup N, Jørgensen C et al. (2015): Prenatal detection of congenital heart disease in a low risk population undergoing

- first and second trimester screening. *Prenatal Diagnosis*, 35 (4): 325-330.
14. Rydberg C, Tunon K. Detection of fetal abnormalities by second-trimester ultrasound screening in a non-selected population. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand* 2017; 96:176-82.
 15. EUROCAT Central Registry, 2010. Special Report: Prenatal Screening Policies in Europe 2010. (<https://www.orpha.net/actor/Orphanews/2010/doc/Special-Report-Prenatal-Screening-Policies.pdf>).
 16. Oakley GP Jr. Frequency of human congenital malformations. *Clin Perinatol*. 1986;13(3):545-54.
 17. Parker SE, Mai CT, Canfield MA, et al. Updated National Birth Prevalence estimates for selected birth defects in the United States, 2004-2006. *Birth Defects Res A Clin Mol Teratol*. 2010;88(12):1008-16.
 18. Sallout B, Obedat N, Shakeel F, et al. Prevalence of major congenital anomalies at King Fahad Medical City in Saudi Arabia: a tertiary care centre-based study. *Ann Saudi Med*. 2015; 35(5):343-51.
 19. Sheridan E, Wright J, Small N, et al. Risk factors for congenital anomaly in a multiethnic birth cohort: an analysis of the Born in Bradford study. *Lancet*. 2013;382(9901):1350-9.
 20. Ngo AD, Taylor R, Roberts CL. Paternal exposure to Agent Orange and spina bifida: a meta-analysis. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 2010;25(1):37-44.
 21. Nakling J, Backe B. Routine ultrasound screening and detection of congenital anomalies outside a university setting. *Acta Obstetrica et Gynecologica Scandinavica*. 2005;84(11):1042-8.
 22. Souka AP, Pilalis A, Kavalakis I. Screening for major structural abnormalities at the 11- to 14-week ultrasound scan. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2006;194(2):393-6.
 23. Sallout BI, Al-Hashan MS, Attyyaa RA. Antenatal diagnosis, prevalence and outcome of major congenital anomalies in Saudi Arabia: a hospital based study. *Ann Saudi Med*. 2008; 28(4):272-6.
 24. Alia N, Ahmed I. Congenital anomalies: prevalence of abnormalities in 2nd trimester of pregnancy in Madina teaching hospital, Faisalabad on grey scale ultrasound. *JUMDC*. 2010; 1(1):23-8.
 25. Yanuarman, Aziz MA, Mose JC. Congenital anomalies: Case Review January 1st 2011 - December 31st 2013 Period in The Sakura Fetomaternal Diagnosis Unit Dr. Hasan Sadikin General Hospital, Bandung Fetomaternal Division of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology Faculty of Medicine, Padjadjaran University / Dr. Hasan Sadikin General Hospital, Bandung Indonesia. 2015.
 26. Naseha A, Iqbal Y. Incidence of congenital anomalies in tertiary health care centre. *Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences-Jemds* 2016; 5 (67): 4826-4833.
 27. Christianson R, van den Berg B, Milkovich L et al. Incidence of congenital anomalies among white and black live births with long-term follow up. *American Journal of Public Health* 1981;71 (12): 1333-1341.
 28. Nayab A, Irshad A, Amir HM, Nazia P. Congenital anomalies: prevalence of congenital abnormalities 2nd trimester of pregnancy in Madina Teaching Hospital, Faisalabad on gray scale ultrasound. *JUMDC*. 2010;1(1):23- 28.
 29. Alakananda, Choudhury SS, Neiting C. A study on prevalence of congenital anomalies of foetuses among pregnant women in a tertiary care hospital and its association with socio-demographic factors. *The New Indian Journal of OBGYN*. 2015;2(1):46-50.
 30. Agarwal SS. Neural tube defect: a preventable congenital malformation. *Indian Pediatr*. 1999; 36: 643-8.
 31. Perveen F, Tyyab S. Frequency and pattern of distribution of congenital anomalies in newborn and associated maternal risk factors. *J Coll Physician Surg Pak*. 2007;17(6):340-3.
 32. Iliescu D, Tudorache S, Comanescu A, et al. Improved detection rate of structural abnormalities in the first trimester using an extended examination protocol. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol*. 2013;42(3):300-9.
 33. Manegold G, Tercanli S, Struben H, Huang D, Kang A. Is a routine ultrasound in the third trimester justified? Additional fetal anomalies diagnosed after two previous unremarkable ultrasound examinations. *Ultraschall Med*. 2011; 32(4):381-6.
 34. Skråstad RB, Eik-Nes SH, Sviggum O, et al. A randomized controlled trial of third-trimester routine ultrasound in a non-selected population. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand*. 2013;92(12):1353-60.
 35. Center for disease prevention and control. Health Statistics Database. (https://statistika.spkc.gov.lv/pxweb/en/Health/Health_Mates_berna_veseliba/MCH035_antenat_dzemd.px/table/tableViewLayout2/ [last accessed 15.02.2022.]).
 36. Ferrier Clément, Dhombres Ferdinand, Khoshnood Babak, Randrianaivo Hanitra, Perthuis Isabelle, et al. Trends in resource use and effectiveness of ultrasound detection of fetal structural anomalies in France: a multiple registry-based study. *BMJ Open* 2019;9(2):e025482.

37. Ding Wen-Ping, Li Nan, Chen Min. Ultra-
sound screening of fetal anomalies at 11–13+6

weeks. *Matern-Fetal Med* 2020;2(3):175–80.